

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

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MUNDARIJA

YASHIL TRANSPORT SIYOSATINING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH VA TARMOQLARARO INTEGRATSIYADAGI O'RNI.....	21
Rahmonov Rasul Ne'matovich	
BANK AKTIVLARI VA PASSIVLARINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	34
Safarov Sanjar Ravshan o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONNING INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISH STRATEGIYALARI.....	38
Madraximova Irodaxon Sherzodbek qizi	
HUDUDIY XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA MENEJMENT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA MODELII	43
Maxmudova Nozimaxon Baxriddinxonovna	
DAVLATNING BUDJET SIYOSATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI.....	50
A.A. Ismailov	
DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIGINING MEXANIZMINI SAMARALI TASHKILLASHTIRISHDA MOLIVAVIY MANBALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNI YO'NALISHLARI	56
Mansurov Mansur Alisherovich	
ANTIKRIZISLI BOSHQARUV TIZIMLARIDA RANGLI SIGNAL MEXANIZMLARINING FUNKSIYALARI.....	61
Aliqulov Aziz Haydarjonovich	
XODIMLARNI MOTIVATSIYALASHNING XALQARO MODELLARINI O'ZBEKISTON KORXONALARIDA QO'LLASH IMKONIYATLARI.....	66
Yormamatov Qodirjon Juraqulovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT OMILLARI VA ULARNING QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARINING SAMARADORLIGIGA TA'SIRI.....	71
Yaxshiyev Shahzod Sherali o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARI VA MEHNAT BOZORI INTEGRATSIYASI BO'YICHA XORIJ TAJRIBALARI.....	78
Haqqulov Fazliddin Faxriddinovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHDA RIVOJLANGAN VA RIVOJLANAYOTGAN DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	84
Aripov Abdulaziz Sakijonovich	
YASHIL ENERGETIKA RIVOJLANISHINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI EKONOMETRIK BAHOLASH.....	89
Bobokulova Muhabbat Mahammadiyeva	
ELEKTRON TO'LOVLAR VA POS TIZIMLARI — KICHIK BIZNESDA SAMARASI VA XAVFLARI	93
To'liqinov Dilshodxo'ja Olim o'g'li	
MINTAQADA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI	98
Yusubov In'omjon Ikram o'g'li	
SOLIQ SIYOSATINI RAQAMLI BOSHQARISH ORQALI BUDJET DAROMADLARINI BARQARORLASHTIRISH STRATEGIYASI.....	103
Xodjimatov Xamidullo Mamirjonovich	
OZIQ-OVQAT TOVARLARI B2B BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA ZAMONAVIY MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH	108
Hayitboyeva Ullijon Bobonazar qizi	
FARMASEVTIKA SANOATIDA INVESTITSION FAOLIYAT SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH	113
Yaqubov Timurbek G'anibekovich	
SHAXSNI OVOZI ASOSIDA IDENTIFIKATSIYALASH VA AUTENTIFIKATSIYALASH ALGORITMLARI	123
Ozoda Sabirova Shermamaxamatovna	

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT — BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH GENERATORI	129
Berdibekova Dilfuza Xoldorbekovna	
CHET EL MEHMONXONA TARMOQLARINING BRENDING STRATEGIYALARINI O'RGANISH	133
Ergashev Oybek Mamarasul o'g'li	
MILLIY IQTISODIYOTDA KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK SOHASINING MOLIVAVIY SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHNING USLUBIY JIHLATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	144
Arzikulov Otabek Ali o'g'li	
TRANSPORT TIZIMI SOHASI KORXONALARINING INNOVATSION SALOHİYATINI BAHOLASH YO'NALISHLARI	152
Ismailov Akmal Maxsudovich, Abilqosimova Shaxlo Sodiq qizi	
MEHMONXONALAR SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA XODIMLARINING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI	158
Abdusamadov Sarvar Adxamovich, Normurodov Tal'at Normurod o'g'li	
KORXONALARDA HR TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	163
Aminova Shaxnoza Aziz qizi	
JAHON IQTISODIYOTIDA OZIYQ-OVQAT XAFSIZLIK RO'LI	168
Abdusamatov Barkamol Rustamjon o'g'li	
ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИЕ РЕСУРСЫ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАНА И СУЩЕСТВУЮЩАЯ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРА	174
Хошимова Камилла Навфал қизи	
DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK MEXANIZMLARI: REKREATIONS TURIZM SOHASIDA QO'LLASH TAJRIBASI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	184
Najmitdinov G'ayratbek Sharifovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA VIRTUAL TA'LIM PLATFORMALARI: TEXNIK VA PEDAGOGIK TALABLAR, TIZIMLI TAHLIL VA IQTISODIY JIHLATLAR	189
Turayeva Adiba Ikramovna	
ICHKI AUDIT TIZIMI VA UNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	193
Nuridinova Barchinoy Xusniddin qizi	
MINTAQA IQTISODIYOTIDA SUV RESURSLARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	199
Xaitbaev Jasurbek Otaxanovich	
MINTAQANING EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMI	204
Raimboyeva Mashhura Davronbek qizi	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	210
Jobborov Anvar Egamberdiyevich	
ISLOMIY MOLIVALASHTIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA SUN'IY INTELEKTNING DOLZARBLIGI	217
Nazarov Nodirjon Namoz o'g'li	
JISMONIY SHAXSLARNING MOL-MULKINI SOLIQQA TORTISH MASALALARI	222
Mamadjanov Shuxrat Jalolidinovich	
ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND BUSINESS MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	225
Abdukhalikova Komila Abdukhalikovna	
BANKLARDA BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASH UCHUN RAQAMLI YECHIMLARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	229
Saydamatova Muxlisabonu Rasuljon qizi	
PAXTA-TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATINI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH YO'NALISHLARI: TAHLIL VA TAKLIFLAR	233
Abdullayev Hamidulla Abdug'ani o'g'li	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF STATE FINANCIAL REGULATION MECHANISMS IN ENSURING THE CAPITALIZATION OF INSURANCE ORGANIZATIONS	238
Abdullaev Erkinjon Azamovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA YASHIL MOLIVALASHTIRISHNING NAZARIY JIHLATLARI	245
Xalikov S. X.	

QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI BOZORIDA KORXONALAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHDA MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH	245
<i>Xudayberganov Jasur Baxodirovich</i>	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF STATE FINANCIAL REGULATION MECHANISMS IN ENSURING THE CAPITALIZATION OF INSURANCE ORGANIZATIONS	251
<i>Abdullaev Erkinjon Azamovich</i>	
NATIJAVIYLIKKA YO'NALTIRILGAN BudgetLASHTIRISH JARAYONINING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI VA UNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	257
<i>Allakuliyev Akmal Baltayevich</i>	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	261
<i>Jobborov Anvar Egamberdiyevich</i>	
TO'QIMACHILIK KORXONALARIDA BOSHQARUV TIZIMINI RESURSLARNI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH ORQALI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	268
<i>Avulchayeva Feruza Jurakuziyevna</i>	
BANKLARDA BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASH UCHUN RAQAMLI YECHIMLARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	272
<i>Saydamatova Muxlisabonu Rasuljon qizi</i>	
ZAMONAVIY ISH JOYLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA AYOLLARNING ROLI	276
<i>Tulyaganova Aziza</i>	
ISLOMIY MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA SUN'IY INTELLEKTNING DOLZARBLIGI.....	281
<i>Nazarov Nodirjon Namoz o'g'li</i>	
TURIZM MARKETINGINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI, ZAMONAVIY YO'NALISHLARI VA UNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	286
<i>Xamidov Otabek Bakidjanovich</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK SOHASINING IQTISODIY KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMINI STATISTIK BAHOLASHNING USLUBIY JIHATLARI	290
<i>Arzikulov Otabek Ali o'g'li</i>	
ЭКОЛОГАМ ПОЧЕТ И УВАЖЕНИЕ	298
<i>Максудова Шахиста</i>	
DEBITOR VA KREDITOR QARZDORLIKNING MOHIYATI VA ULARNING O'ZGARISH TENDENTSIYALARI	304
<i>Jo'raev Farruxbek Muxiddin o'g'li</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ISLOMIY MOLIYALASHTIRISH XIZMATLARI BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	307
<i>Inomjonov Islomjon Iloxomjon o'g'li</i>	
ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND BUSINESS MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	311
<i>Abdukhalkova Komila Abdukhalkovna</i>	
МОБИЛЬНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ КАК СРЕДСТВО ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ БУДУЩИХ ИНЖЕНЕРОВ.....	315
<i>Хурамова Фарангиз Учкун кизи</i>	
ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИЯ НАЛОГОВ И АКЦИЗНАЯ РЕФОРМА УЗБЕКИСТАНА В WTO	319
<i>Дамир Рустамович Абдулов</i>	
BANK TIZIMIDAGI ISLOHOTLAR SHAROITIDA LIKVIDLILIK RISKINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	324
<i>Alimov Baxtiyor Murodovich</i>	
BANK AUDITINING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI VA UNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	335
<i>Narziyev Xayotjon Azamatovich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA SOHASIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI QO'LLASH MASALALARI.....	343
<i>Abdimuminova Saodat Taxirjonovna</i>	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOAT MAXSULOTLARI EKSPORT FAOLIYATI TAHLILI VA BRENDDA LIDERLIK TUSHUNCHALARI.....	352
<i>Abdulazizova Xushnoza Nayabovna</i>	

ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНО-ПРАВОВЫЕ МОДЕЛИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОТХОДАМИ НА ОСНОВЕ ОПЫТА РАЗВИТЫХ СТРАН И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ИХ АДАПТАЦИИ В УСЛОВИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	357
Д. Мейлиева	
О‘ZBEKISTON AUDITORLIK TIZIMIDA KASBDOSHLAR TOMONIDAN VAHOLASH (PEER REVIEW) TIZIMINI JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI	361
Parpiyev Jaxongir Iloxomjonovich	
ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ И БОЛЬШИЕ ДАННЫЕ (BIG DATA) В УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКИХ РЕШЕНИЯХ.....	366
Шарипов Бахтиёр Михлибаевич	
О‘ZBEKISTONDA SUVGA BO‘LGAN TALABNI VAQTLI QATORLAR ORQALI TAHLIL QILISH	375
Sarvar Mamasoliyev	
BOSHQARUV VA NAZORAT MAQSADLARIDA XARAJATLAR HISOBINI TASHKIL ETISH	383
Isomuxamedov Akbarjon Boxodir o‘g‘li	
MINTAQALAR BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHINI TA‘MINLASHNING ASOSIY YO‘NALISHLARI.....	389
Salomat NOROVA	
О‘ZBEKISTON TURIZM BRENД BOZORINING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA TENDENSIYALARI.....	394
Zufarov Akmal Gulamiddinovich	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOTDA QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA MANBALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH METODOLOGIYASI.....	404
Qodirov Baxodirjon Tursunovich	
О‘ZBEKISTON SOLIQ TIZIMINI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISHDA YAGONA INTERAKTIV DAVLAT XIZMATLARI PORTALINING O‘RNI VA AHAMIYATI	408
Dehqonov G‘ayratjon Raximovich	
OLIY TA‘LIM MUASSASALARIDA INNOVATSION HAMDA TIJORATLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	414
Inoyatov Mardonbek Mo‘min o‘g‘li	
OLIY IQTISODIY TA‘LIM ORQALI EKO-INNOVATSIYALAR VA “YASHIL” INVESTITSIYALARNI RAG‘BATLANTIRISH MEХANIZMLARI: SIYOSIY VA INSTITUTSIONAL DOIRALAR	418
Xasanova Zarina Maxamadaliyeva	
XODIMLAR MALAKASINI OSHIRISH — ZAMON TALABI.....	427
Narzullaev Oybek Narzullaevich	
BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI YURITISHDA JURNAL-ORDER SHAKLINING AHAMIYATI.....	433
Axmedjanov Abdufato	
KENDALL VA SPEARMAN TARTIBIY KORRELYATSIYA Koeffitsiyentlari asosida YASHIL IQTISODIYOT INDIKATORLARINING STATISTIK O‘ZARO TA‘SIRINI MODELLASHTIRISH	437
Muradov Rustamjon Sobitxonovich	
ИНТЕНСИВНЫЕ И ЭКСТЕНСИВНЫЕ ОГРАНИЧЕНИЯ В РЕГУЛИРОВАНИИ СПРОСА.....	442
Аминджанова Румейса Батыровна, Камилова Наргиза Абдукажоровна	
ИНКЛЮЗИВНЫЙ ПОДХОД В ТУРИЗМЕ: ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ И УЗБЕКСКАЯ ПРАКТИКА	445
Азимова Шахло Таировна	
AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARIDA MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTNING XAQARO STANDARTLARIGA O‘TISHNING HOLATI VA TAHLILI	450
Bayjanov Sarsengaliy Xalmuratovich	
UZUM EKSPORT QILUVCHI KOMPANIYALARDA YASHIL O‘TISH JARAYONINI QO‘LLAB-QUVVATLASH UCHUN EKO-MARKETING VA AYLANMA IQTISODIYOT TAMOIYILLARINI INTEGRATSIYALASH.....	454
Usmonova Diyora Mahmud qizi	
UMUMTA‘LIM MAKTABLARIDA XARAJATLAR SMETASI VA SHTATLAR JADVALINING TAHLILI: OPTIMALLASHTIRISH VA SAMARADORLIKNING YANGICHA USULLARI (NAMANGAN VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	461
Umarov Avzaljon Yodgorali o‘g‘li	
INVESTITSIYALARNING KIRIB KELISHIGA TO‘SQINLIK QILUVCHI MUAMMOLARNI BARTARAF ETISH YO‘LLARI.....	467
Alimova Dilafro‘z Tohir qizi	

FARMATSEVTIKA KORXONALARIDA MOLIYAVIY HISOBOT SHAKLLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA INVESTORLAR UCHUN AXBOROT OCHIQLIGINI TA'MINLASH	470
Turdikulova Gulshad Nurmatovna	
ISHLAB CHIQRISH KORXONALARIDA MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTLARNING SHAFFOFLIGINI OSHIRISHDA MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTNING XALQARO STANDARTLARINING AHAMIYATI	477
Uztemirov Alisher Aktam o'g'li	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA SANOAT TARMOQLARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI TA'MINLASHGA YO'NALTIRILGAN BANDLIK TUZILMASINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH	482
Tursunov Bekmuxammad Omonovich	
XORIY TAJRIBALARIDA SOLIQ BAZASINI ANIQLASH TARTIBI METODOLOGIYASINING MAVJUD METODLARI VA ULARNING XUSUSIYATLARI	489
Xalikchayeva Sadokat Ilxomjonovna	
IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNING KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI VA UNING MAMLAKAT IQTISODIYOTIDAGI O'RNI	496
Ramatillaev M.R.	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI SUG'URTALASH VA DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	502
Eshboyev Shahobiddin Anorqul o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARI O'RTASIDAGI RAQOBATNI BAHOLASH VA KUCHAYTIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY METODOLOGIYASI: O'ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI	506
Qulmetov Mansurbek Ro'zmatovich	
XALQARO REYTING TASHKILOTLARINING OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIGA TA'SIRI VA MAVJUD PLATFORMALAR	515
O'rozboyev Xayrulla Murodboy o'g'li	
TALABALAR MOTIVATSIYASINING MEXANIZMLARI: LOYIHA ASOSIDAGI TA'LIM TEKNOLOGIYALARIDA	523
Kasimova (Mulladjanova) Nasiba Azimdjanovna	
ISH KUCHIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH VA NORASMIY BANDLIKNI SOYADAN CHIQRISH BO'YICHA TAKLIFLAR ISHLAB CHIQISH	531
Pulatov Dilshod Xaqberdiyevich, Maxkamova Shaxlo Yulchiyevna, Absamatov Baxrom Danakulovich	
KASBIY TA'LIM MAZMUNIDA TA'LIM VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH INTEGRATSIYASINI RAG'BATLANTIRISH ORQALI O'RTA BO'G'IN KADRLAR TAYYORLASHNING JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	538
Tojiyev Sirojiddin Sayriddinovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TURIZM INFRATUZILMASINI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINING TURLARI VA SHAKLLARI	542
Muminova Mavjuda Sharifovna	
SUV RESURSLARIDAN FOYDALANISHNI STRATEGIK BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGI MASALALARI	547
Kadirhodjayeva Nilufar Rahmatullayevna	
MHXSGA MUVOFIQ ASOSIY VOSITALAR HISOBINI TASHKIL ETISH MASALALARI	552
Aliyev Sherzod Abdixomidovich	
ФАКТОРЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ	558
Аллаева Г.Ж.	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH SHAROITIDA INVESTITSION MUHITNI YAXSHILASH YO'NALISHLARI	564
Irisqulova Munisa Akmal qizi	
TASHABBUSLI BUDJET JARAYONLARI DOIRASIDA 2024-YILDA AMALGA OSHIRILGAN ISHLAR TAHLILI	569
Xamidov Xabibullo Xikmatulla o'g'li	
MINTAQA SANOATIDA AHOLI JON BOSHIGA YAQQ O'ZGARISHINING DINAMIK TAHLILI	574
Nabiyev G'ulom Abdusalomovich	

INFRATUZILMAVIY INVESTISIYA LOYIHALARINI DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK ASOSIDA MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA RISKLARNI BOSHQARISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBALARI	583
<i>Ergashev Axmadjon Maxmudjon o'g'li</i>	
ПРОБЛЕМЫ ГЛОБАЛЬНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОГО ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ В ЭКОЛОГИИ.....	587
<i>Максудова Шахиста</i>	
PAHTA-TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARINING INVESTITSION FAOLIGINI OSHIRISHNING ILMIY-USLUBIY JIHATLARI	593
<i>B.Sh.Shadmanov</i>	
ECONOMIC INDICATORS OF SUPPLY CHAIN EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN'S EXPORT SECTOR	597
<i>Mukhammadiyaminova Shakhzoda Sherzodovna</i>	
BUDJET TASHKIOTLARIDA BUDJETDAN TASHQARI MABLAG'LAR HISOBI VA ICHKI AUDITNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	602
<i>Muxtorova Maftuna Salohiddin qizi</i>	
RAQAMLASHTIRISH JARAYONIDA BANKLARNING XAVFSIZLIGI VA MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING ILMIY-AMALIY ASOSLARI	607
<i>Aliyeva Umidaxon Xusanboyevna</i>	
XIZMATLAR SOHASI VA KAMBAG'ALLIK O'RTASIDAGI O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIK.....	611
<i>Dawletmuratov Adilbay Mirzabaeovich</i>	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL CLUSTERS BASED ON THE PRINCIPLES OF A "GREEN ECONOMY"	615
<i>Boboqulov Sanjar Baxronkulovich, Kamolov Oybek Faxriddin o'g'li</i>	
ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИОННО-КОММУНИКАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИИ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СВОБОДНЫХ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ЗОН В НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ.....	620
<i>Халимжанов Дилшод Эргашбекович</i>	
YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI VA O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	626
<i>Mavlyanov Muzaffar Yusupovich</i>	
NAMANGAN VILOYATI TURIZM SOHASINING SO'NGGI YILLARDA RIVOJLANISHI VA STATISTIK TAHLILI	630
<i>Kuymuratova Matlubaxon Abdimanabovna</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI EKSPORTINING IQTISODIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLOVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI	634
<i>Faxriddinov Bahriddin</i>	
INNOVATSION SHAROITDA TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH	640
<i>Sattarov Ilkhomjon Rahimjanovich</i>	
IQLIM O'ZGARISHI SHAROITIDA SUV RESURSLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI	645
<i>Nurmatov Norbek Jo'rayevich</i>	
MINTAQA LOGISTIK XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING INNOVATSION VA INSTITUTSIONAL ISTIQBOLLARI	652
<i>Xalimov Javlonbek Shaxriyorovich</i>	
KORXONALARNING BANKROTLIK EHTIMOLINI SUN'IY INTELLEKT YORDAMIDA PROGNOZLASH	659
<i>Zaynutdinov Ismoil Samariddin o'g'li</i>	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ ФИНАНСОВЫХ РЫНКОВ	665
<i>Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович</i>	
MEDIA LOYIHALARINI BOSHQARISH: O'ZBEKISTON OAV AMALIYOTI TAHLILI	673
<i>Yo'ldosheva Dilobar Jaxongir qizi</i>	
O'QITISH NATIJALARINI ZAMONAVIY BAHOLASH TAMOYILLARI	677
<i>Abdullayeva Sanobar Berdiyevna, Xujakulov Shaxriyor Shokir o'g'li</i>	
MALAYZIYADA PROGRESSIV VA INKLYUZIV ISLOMIY MOLIYA TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH: 2024-YIL TAJRIBASI VA NATIJALARI	681
<i>Safarova Nasiba Gulmurod qizi</i>	

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ ПРОВЕДЕНИЯ ПРОЦЕДУР ДЬЮ-ДИЛИДЖЕНС В АКЦИОНЕРНЫХ ОБЩЕСТВАХ.....	687
<i>Прокудина Кристина Александровна</i>	
HUDUDLARDA INVESTITSIYA SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	692
<i>Xalilova Madinabonu Abduraxmon qizi</i>	
LIZING MUOMALALARI HISOBINI XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	701
<i>Baxadirov Alisher Komilovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING JISMONIY SHAXSLAR DEPOZITLARI VA ULARNI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	705
<i>Melikov Otabek Maxmadaminovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RAQAMLASHTIRISH VA EKOTIZIMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	711
<i>Erkinova Feruza Najmitdinovna</i>	
DAVLAT SEKTORIDA ICHKI NAZORAT TIZIMINI BAHOLASHDA SUN'IY INTELEKTDAN FOYDALANISH: XAVF YOKI IMKONIYAT	717
<i>Ostonokulov Azamat Abduraximovich, Tadjiyev Erkin Muxitdinovich</i>	
SUN'IY VA KIMYOVIY TOLALARNING TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA EKOLOGIK BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHDAGI O'RNI	723
<i>Raximov Furqat Jalolovich</i>	
OLIY TA'LIM MASSASALARINING MOLIVAVIY RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISH MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	728
<i>Mahmudov Akbar Abduraximovich</i>	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLAR.....	733
<i>Abdullayev Suyun Artikovich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA AVTOMOBILSOZLIK KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA JARAYONLARI: "UZAUTO MOTORS" AJ AMALIYOTI VA NATIJALARI.....	737
<i>Allabergenov Azamat Joldasbayevich</i>	
WAYS TO USE MARKETING DATA IN THE MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISE VALUATION PROCESS	742
<i>Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna</i>	
KICHIK SANOAT KORXONALARI O'RTASIDAGI ISHLAB CHIQRISH VA KOOPERATIV ALOQALAR HOLATI.....	747
<i>Boyturayev Olimjon Urayimovich</i>	
BANK RISKLARI VA ULARNI TA'SIRINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISHDA STATISTIK HISOBTLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	753
<i>Kamoldinov Sardorbek Maxammadsobir o'g'li</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA AYOLLARNING ISH BILAN BANDLIGINI OSHIRISH IMKONIYATLARI	761
<i>Eshqobulova Charos O'roq qizi</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONNING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH KONSEPSIYASI: TARIXIY MEROS VA ZAMONAVIY YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALAR UYG'UNLIGI.....	766
<i>Azimova Shohista Salohiddinovna</i>	
SOLIQ TIZIMIDA RAQAMLI MARKIROVKALANGAN TOVARLARNI RAQAMLASHTIRISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MUAMMOLARI	770
<i>Muxammadov Nodir Karimovich</i>	
BIZNES JARAYONLARINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISHDA "LEAN MANAGEMENT" TIZIMINI JORIY ETISHNING ILMIY ASOSLARI	775
<i>Muhiddinov Ozodbek Ikromjon o'g'li, Shakirova Gulrux Po'latjon qizi, Ozodbek Musayev</i>	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASINING TURISTIK POTENTIALI UMUMIY TAVSIFI.....	783
<i>Madaminova Sanobar Askarovna</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES KORXONALARIDA EKSPORT MAHSULOTLARI ISHLAB CHIQRISH KONSEPSIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	789
<i>Boymirzayev Zokirjon Mashrabboyevich</i>	
AHOLINING TURMUSH DARAJASI VA UNING KO'RSATKICHLARI.....	794
<i>Sayitbayev Shermirza Datkamirzayevich</i>	

KORXONA ASOSIY XO'JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKT SIFATIDA AHAMIYATI.....	799
Yuldashova Yoqutoy Murodjon qizi, Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdulkarimovich	
DAVLAT ISHTIROKIDAGI KORXONALARNI XUSUSIYLASHTIRISH JARAYONIDA KADRLAR SALOHİYATINI SAQLAB QOLISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISH STRATEGIYALARI.....	803
Bekchanov Ruslan Ambiyatovich	
PARALLEL KORPUS ASOSIDA INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIK ATAMALARINING EKVIVALENTLIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	807
Yulduz Xalilova Nasriddinova	
KOLBASA VA GO'SHT MAHSULOTLARI ISHLAB CHIQRISHDA CHIQRINDISIZ ISHLAB CHIQRISH ("ZERO WASTE") MODELINING ROLI: XORIJIY TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDAGI AMALIY YO'NALISHLAR.....	810
Eshtemirova Anora Norboy qizi	
EKSPORTYO'R KORXONALARDA TOVAR VA XIZMATLAR EKSPORTI BO'YICHA QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT VA FOYDA SOLIG'INI TO'G'RI HISOBLANISHI TAHLILI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	814
Sobirova Xilola Rustam qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TO'QIMACHILIK VA TIKUV-TRIKOTAJ SANOATI RIVOJLANISHINING MILLIY RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI OSHIRISHDAGI O'RNI.....	819
Ikramova Taxmina Latifovna	
YANGI RIVOJLANAYOTGAN BOZORLARIDA HR QAROR QABUL QILISH JARAYONINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA IQTISODIY TA'LIMNING ROLI.....	824
Dilfuza Shokirova	
UZOQ MUDDATLI AKTIVLAR HISOBINI XALQARO BUXGALTERIYA STANDARTLARI ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	833
Abdiev Mutolib Anvar o'g'li	
DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK TIZIMINING NAZARIY VA USLUBIY ASOSLARI.....	838
Raximjonova Shohsanam Baxodirovna	
AKTIVLAR VA MAJBURIYATLARNI MHXS ASOSIDA BAHOLASHNING ZARURIYATI VA AHAMIYATI.....	842
G'anibayev Iloxomjon Shokiraliyevich	
XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB QILISH JARAYONINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI VA HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISH BILAN BOG'LIQLIGI.....	847
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, Turdimuratova Aziza Alisherovna	
AGRAR ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHDA "QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI-4.0" VA "AQLLI QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI" KONSEPSIYALARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH.....	851
Yusupov Muxiddin Soatovich	
PAXTA-TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARINI MOLIYALASHTIRISH MANBALARINI GURUHLASH VA BAHOLASH.....	860
Davlyatov Bekzodjon Aslanxojayevich	
TA'LIM TIZIMINI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XORIY TAJRIBASINING AHAMIYATI.....	864
Sobirov Shaxzod Ozod o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINI SOLIQQA TORTISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI.....	868
Karimov Mirolimjon Karimjon o'g'li	
ПРОБЛЕМЫ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА В ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОМ РАЗВИТИИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	875
Аликулов С. А., Хамракулова О. Д.	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDA KORXONALAR BOSHQARUV MEKANIZMLARINING EVOLYUTSIYASI: KONSEPTUAL TAHLIL.....	880
Nabiev Bobur Muhammadqosim o'g'li	
SUD-HUQUQ TIZIMINI YANADA DEMOKRATLASHTIRISH: JORIY HOLATI, MUAMMOLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	884
Majidov Muslimbek Maxamadjon o'g'li	

IQTISODIYOTNI LIBERALLASHTIRISH SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA KLASTERLARNI TASHKIL ETISHNING TASHKILY-HUQUQIY ASOSLARI	889
Xo'jageldiyev Chorshanbi Pardayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA ZAMONAVIY INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH	893
Shaymanova Nigora Yusupovna	
XO'JALIK FAOLIYATINI SAMARADORLIGI VA BIZNES HOLATINI BAHOLASH	899
Abdukarimova Muslima Abduaziz qizi, Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdugarimovich	
CROSS-BORDER E-COMMERCE IN CENTRAL ASIA.....	904
Bakhtiyorjon Komilov	
O'ZBEKISTONDA NORASMIY SEKTOR ISHCHILARINING PENSIYA TA'MINOTI MASALALARI.....	908
Abdulazizova Nargiza Baxodir qizi	
KORXONA VA TASHKILOTLARDA QOG'OZ SARFINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISHDA JAHON TAJRIBASI	913
Oripov Mirzo Mahmudovich	
ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В ЗАЩИТЕ ВНУТРЕННЕГО РЫНКА ОТ КОНТРАФАКТНОЙ ПРОДУКЦИИ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН).....	917
Ибраимова Махсура Уснатдин кизи	
KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARIDA BOSHQARUV TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	922
Xasanova Robiyaxon Kamoliddin qizi	
THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES ON THE PROCESSES OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN THE INSURANCE INDUSTRY.....	927
D.D.Omonova	
THE ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE GLOBAL ECONOMY AND THEIR STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT	933
Yovkochev Sherzod	
YURIDIK SHAXSLARNI YIRIK SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILAR TOIFASIGA KIRITISH MEZONLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	941
To'raqulov Bekzod Hazratqul o'g'li	
BUTUNJAHON SAVDO TASHKILOTIGA A'ZO BO'LISHDA SOLIQ TIZIMINI TRANSFORMATSIYA QILISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI.....	945
Xojakbar Zaynabidinov	
BANK TIZIMIDA TAVAKKALCHILIK TUSHUNCHASI VA UNI BAHOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLARI	950
Malikova Dilrabo Muminovna, Shakarova Kumush Faxriddin qizi	
REAL SEKTOR TARMOQLARINI KREDITLASHDA MOLIVAVIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASH YO'LLARI.....	955
Savurbayev Zafar Abdumuminovich	
INVESTITSIYA JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA IQTISODIY BARQARORLIK OMILLARI VA ULARNING BOSHQARUVI	960
D. G. Bazarov	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK SOHASINI YANADA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH HAMDA KOMPLEKS TIZIMLASHTIRISH	966
Abdullayev Javohir Abdumalik o'g'li	
XIZMATLAR KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSIYA FAOLIYATINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH VA BOSHQARISH: IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA ISTIQBOLLI TAVSIYALAR	971
Xudayberdiyeva Nargiza Nizomiddin qizi	
MINTAQADA KICHIK BIZNES KORXONALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	976
Ergashev Jamshid Jamoliddinovich	
TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARIDA INNOVATSION MAHSULOTLARNI ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	981
Mirzayev Kobil Nosirjonovich	

PUL AYLANMASINI TASHKIL QILISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI VA O'ZBEKISTONDA FOYDALANISHNING IMKONIYATLARI.....	987
Gadoyev So'hrob Jumakulovich	
MARKETING VA TOVAR STRATEGIYALARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH	993
Ibadullayeva Sevara Allashukurovna, Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdukarimovich	
PILLACHILIK SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INVESTITSIYA VA DAVLAT KO'MAGIGA OID METODOLOGIK YONDASHUVLAR	998
Xudoykulov Mamarasul Radjabovich	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDAGI KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNING QURILISH SOHASIDAGI ULUSHINING TREND MODELLARI ORQALI TAHLILI	1005
Mamatkulova Xurshida Nasrullayevna	
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASES OF TEXTILE PRODUCTS MARKET SEGMENTATION	1012
Ibaydullaeva Feruza Kholjuraevna	
O'ZBEKISTONNING JINOIY FAOLIYATDAN OLINGAN DAROMADLARNI LEGALLASHTIRISHGA QARSHI KURASH TIZIMIGA SUN'YI INTELLEKTNI INTEGRATSIYASI: BANK SEKTORIDA JORIY ETISHNING POTENSIALI VA TO'SIQLARINI BAHOLASH	1018
Rashidov Avazbek Raximovich	
UZOQ MUDDATLI AKTIVLAR HISOBINI XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	1025
Shermatov Sirojiddan Xaydarovich	
РОЛЬ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В УСОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИИ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ РЕЗУЛЬТАТИВНОСТИ КОМПОНЕНТОВ ПРОЕКТА «БЕЗОПАСНЫЙ ГОРОД»	1029
Иминов Акбаржон Одилжонович	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH TARMOQLARIDA BOSHQARUV SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH	1034
Tleubergenov Raxat Shahibaevich	
THE ROLE OF ESG IN ADVANCING CORPORATE REFORMS IN UZBEKISTAN	1038
Zakhidov Azizbek Rustamovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA MARKETING ROLI ORQALI IQTISODIY SIYOSATGA TA'SIRI.....	1043
Egamberdiyev Muzaffar	
DAVLAT BUDJETI JARAYONINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI	1046
Nosirov Islombek Xurram o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA JISMONIY SHAXSLARDAN OLINADIGAN DAROMAD SOLIG'INING PROGRESSIV STAVKASINI JORIY ETISH MEXANIZMI	1052
Pulatov Dilshod Xaqberdiyevich, Mamatkulov Salimjon Raxmonkulovich, Xujamuradov Abrorbek Ro'zimirat o'g'li, Otabekov Otajon G'ayrat o'g'li, Abdiyev Mansur Musurmonovich	
KORXONANING MODDIY BAZASI	1060
Ozodova Shahzoda Ulug'bek qizi	
FINTECH-STARTAPLAR VA TIJORAT BANKLARI HAMKORLIGI: SINERGETIK INTEGRATSIYA VA INNOVATSION EKOTIZIM SHAKLLANISHI	1064
Normo'minov Temurbek Sheraliyevich	
DAVLAT FUQAROLIK XIZMATCHILARINING MEHNATIGA HAQ TO'LASHDA YANGI YAGONA TARIF SETKASINI JORIY ETISH MASALALARI	1069
Oqiljonov Azizjon Olimjon o'g'li	
ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ДИСТАНЦИОННЫХ БАНКОВСКИХ УСЛУГ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ	1074
Хасилова Висола Шоохоровна	
HARD WORK, INDEBTEDNESS AND HOPE: A SOCIO-ECONOMIC LOOK OF MODERN LABOR	1078
Rakhmatullayev Sarvar Nazar o'g'li, Abdukarimova Muborak Sharaf qizi, Madrakhimova R. G.	

HARD WORK, INDEBTEDNESS AND HOPE: A SOCIO-ECONOMIC LOOK OF MODERN LABOR

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Abstract. This article is weak in the relations between man and the economy, but is based on a deep interaction. We are going to talk about human nature is based up statistical data, graphs, and reports; feeling such as fear, shame, hope, and compulsion. The study is not just about working hours, inflation, or loans, it shows how a person's life is affected by the mechanisms of existence.

Key words: economy, credits, real earnings, social justice, monetary pressure, contemporary worker.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola inson va iqtisodiyot o'rtasidagi munosabatlar yuzaki tasvirlangandek tuyulishi mumkin, ammo aslida ular chuqur o'zaro ta'sirga asoslangan. Biz inson tabiatini statistik ma'lumotlar, grafiklar yoki hisobotlar orqali emas, balki qo'rquv, uyat, umid va majburiyat kabi hissiyotlar orqali yoritmoqchimiz. Tadqiqot faqat ish soatlari, inflyatsiya yoki kreditlar haqida emas, balki iqtisodiy jarayonlar inson hayotining mavjudlik mexanizmlariga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishini ochib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiyot, kreditlar, real daromadlar, ijtimoiy adolat, moliyaviy bosim, zamonaviy ishchi.

Аннотация. Данная статья может показаться слабой в описании отношений между человеком и экономикой, однако на самом деле она основывается на глубоком взаимовлиянии. Мы стремимся раскрыть природу человека не через статистические данные, графики и отчеты, а через такие чувства, как страх, стыд, надежда и обязанность. Исследование посвящено не только рабочим часам, инфляции или кредитам, оно показывает, как механизмы существования воздействуют на жизнь человека.

Ключевые слова: экономика, кредиты, реальные доходы, социальная справедливость, финансовое давление, современный работник.

INTRODUCTION

He cut me off, but what Manovikas did was prevent "faith in capital" from becoming the be-all and end-all. On the contrary, life now ends not as mere survival but as something more complex. Just as one month follows another on the calendar, another twelve months now seems absurd only because clarity has finally arrived. Visibility always constitutes progress. Once everyone else has given up, the very exemption reveals how Ihiko thinks: men gather poems, muddling through, gradually discovering what else can be done.

The sight of economic reports and soaring interest rates hanging over us like clenched fists is a form of pressure people today can hardly endure. While Lois and his circle drown themselves in cognac and excess, absolute newcomers still understand nothing about what we should really pay attention to. "If credit becomes everything," one might say, "then are not all human institutions merely exaggerated forms of their smallest interests?"

Will society really refuse to reward tireless labor, and instead charge people according to whatever arm moves where? This is not merely an economic problem; it is a matter of justice. Why should someone who goes to work every day, searching for excitement and meaning in life, still be unable to make ends meet? Why do the rules of economics so often work against him at exactly the moment he begins to get ahead?

This unit does not aim to return you to the economy through numbers and formulas, but to examine human destiny as it intersects with profitability. It adopts a theoretical approach to understanding the mechanisms woven into the “from month to month” life cycle, and the path by which a person might escape it.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The relationship between hard work, financial pressure, and indebtedness has become a central theme in contemporary socio-economic research. Joseph Stiglitz argues that structural imbalances in labor markets, combined with stagnant real wages for low- and middle-income workers, increasingly force households to rely on debt to maintain basic consumption. Thomas Piketty highlights that the concentration of wealth and income in upper segments of society reduces the economic mobility of workers, creating a growing class of individuals who work intensively yet struggle to achieve financial stability.

Studies by the ILO and OECD demonstrate that wage growth across many countries has failed to keep pace with productivity increases, intensifying budget constraints for ordinary households. David Autor’s analysis of technological change shows that automation has eroded middle-skill jobs, pushing workers into lower-paid and insecure positions, which heightens their vulnerability to indebtedness. Research by Maarten Goos and Alan Manning further reveals that the “polarization” of the labor market has deepened reliance on consumer credit among low-income groups.

A major contribution to the understanding of household debt dynamics comes from Atif Mian and Amir Sufi, whose findings from 2014 show that stagnant income growth and expanding credit availability create a systemic pattern where households compensate for declining financial security through borrowing. They conclude that rising household debt is not merely a personal financial issue but a macroeconomic vulnerability that amplifies downturns and increases the likelihood of crises.

From a sociological perspective, Guy Standing introduces the concept of the “precariat,” a class of workers trapped in unstable employment with limited social protections. He argues that increasing job insecurity produces both economic fragility and psychological stress. Arlie Hochschild adds an emotional dimension to labor analysis, showing how modern service work demands continuous emotional effort, which, when paired with financial pressure, produces chronic overwork and burnout.

Research in behavioral economics by Richard Thaler and Cass Sunstein shows that borrowing decisions are often shaped by limited financial literacy, cognitive biases, and aggressive market incentives. Their findings suggest that in many economies—particularly where education, healthcare, or housing expenses are high—workers become indebted not because of irresponsible choices but due to systemic conditions that limit real economic opportunities.

Taken together, the scholarly literature indicates that hard work alone does not guarantee economic security in modern labor markets. Instead, a combination of structural wage stagnation, declining job stability, limited social safety nets, and expanding credit markets creates a cycle in which workers intensify their labor efforts yet fall deeper into debt. At the same time, researchers note that hope for upward mobility and belief in meritocratic progress often motivates workers to continue this cycle, even when economic conditions remain unfavorable.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this research is to analyze the state of affairs of ordinary people in the context of supporting teachers and educating the talented, and to give an account of the reality that although people work extremely hard, they still fail to achieve the prosperity they seek and are increasingly pushed into debt. A closer examination reveals the dynamics included in the research. In other words, the analysis was not based solely on statistical data but also aimed to uncover the economic mechanisms operating behind those numbers. Accordingly, the methodology incorporates several core components.

The first component focuses on analyzing economic indicators. Macroeconomic data such as wages, price levels, inflation, credit volume, and interest rates are examined to compare the decline in average real household incomes with the growth rate of consumer expenditures. This approach makes it possible to assess whether economic pressures are intensifying and to what extent households’ purchasing power is weakening over time.

The next component involves identifying the imbalance between income and expenditure. Here, the analytical concept of “economic disparity” is applied to determine whether wages are sufficient to meet basic

needs. Analytical reports prepared within this framework reveal the underlying economic reasons that drive people toward borrowing, demonstrating that the growing need for loans is not merely a personal financial issue but the result of structural economic pressures.

The final component assesses the social consequences of the credit system. This part of the analysis examines how increasing debt affects people's psychological well-being and intensifies financial pressure. It also highlights that many discounts, relief measures, and temporary financial interventions do not genuinely resolve the crisis but merely postpone its effects, illustrating the fragile and often unsustainable financial lives that many individuals experience.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In this section, the main macroeconomic indicators, average wage, inflation, credit volume, and interest rates were analyzed for Uzbekistan, Russia, Kazakhstan, the USA, and Germany as examples for the period 2015-2023. The wages in Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan have been increasing year by year. This is good news, but on the other hand, an inflation problem still exists, people's real purchasing power is not increasing much as goods are becoming more expensive. This means that the wage has increased but the life has not become easier. In the USA and Germany, the growth is slower but more stable people know that tomorrow will not be worse than today (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Global Wage Dynamics Across Selected Economies (2015–2023)

The chart presents a comparative overview of average monthly wages in Uzbekistan, Russia, Kazakhstan, the United States, and Germany from 2015 to 2023. Overall, all five countries exhibit upward wage trends, although the magnitude and pace of growth differ significantly. The United States consistently maintains the highest wage levels, increasing steadily from around USD 4,700 in 2015 to more than USD 6,100 in 2023, reflecting stable economic expansion and productivity growth. Germany follows a similar trajectory, though at slightly lower levels, rising from approximately USD 4,100 to USD 5,300 over the same period.

In contrast, the post-Soviet economies show much lower wage bases but faster relative growth. Russia's average wage climbs from around USD 500 to roughly USD 900, while Kazakhstan rises from USD 500 to

about USD 800. Uzbekistan, starting from a notably lower level of around USD 200, also demonstrates gradual improvement, reaching nearly USD 450 by 2023.

Inflation has shown its character in every country. In Uzbekistan it remained high for many years, which is connected with the liberalization of prices during the transition period. In Russia, 2015 was a turning point, as after that inflation dropped, but political changes in 2022 once again put pressure on the inflation rate. On the other hand, the US and Germany experienced a sudden rise in inflation during the pandemic, but thanks to the robustness of the financial system, it remained under control (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Cross-Country Inflation Volatility and Global Economic Shocks (2015–2023)

This chart illustrates inflation trends in Uzbekistan, Russia, Kazakhstan, the United States, and Germany over the 2015–2023 period, revealing how domestic economic conditions and global shocks have shaped price dynamics. Uzbekistan exhibits relatively high and fluctuating inflation, peaking above 15% in 2019 before gradually stabilizing toward single-digit levels by 2023. Russia's trajectory shows a sharp decline from 13% in 2015 to under 3% by 2018, followed by renewed inflationary pressure after 2020, culminating in a spike near 14% in 2022—reflecting geopolitical tensions and exchange-rate instability.

Kazakhstan experiences moderate volatility, with inflation rising significantly in 2022 due to supply chain disruptions and regional shocks. Meanwhile, the USA and Germany maintain low and stable inflation for much of the period, though both register pronounced increases in 2021–2022, reaching around 8%—a direct consequence of post-pandemic recovery, energy price surges, and global supply bottlenecks. By 2023, both countries begin returning to moderate levels.

Overall, the data underscores the degree to which global crises synchronize inflation across diverse economies, while structural differences determine the speed of stabilization.

The volume of credit is one of the most important indicators of economic activity. In recent years, loans in Uzbekistan have increased sharply, reaching near-saturation levels in the economy. However, this growth has also contributed to a rise in expenditures — people often take loans not out of real necessity, but simply because access to credit has become easier. In contrast, in countries such as the United States and Germany, large volumes of credit are also observed, but they are not primarily directed toward consumption. Instead, the borrowed funds are invested in production, education, and innovation, thereby stimulating sustainable economic growth (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Expansion of Private Sector Credit and Financial Deepening (2015–2023)

The chart illustrates private sector loans as a percentage of GDP across Uzbekistan, Russia, Kazakhstan, the United States, and Germany from 2015 to 2023, highlighting varying levels of financial deepening and credit expansion. Uzbekistan demonstrates the most rapid upward trajectory, rising from around 20% in 2015 to nearly 65% by 2023. This reflects large-scale banking reforms, increased credit accessibility, and intensified investment activity within the private sector. Russia and Kazakhstan show more moderate and steady trends, stabilizing around the 50–60% range, suggesting cautious lending policies and resilient banking systems despite external shocks.

In advanced economies, credit penetration is significantly higher. The United States leads with consistently elevated levels—rising from 175% to roughly 200%—indicating a mature, highly leveraged financial system with broad access to credit markets. Germany follows a stable but moderate path, fluctuating between 130% and 140%, consistent with its traditionally conservative lending culture.

Overall, the data underscores stark differences in financial system maturity, credit reliance, and economic structure across the selected countries, while confirming a general trend toward increased credit engagement over time.

Interest rates reflect the heartbeat of the country's economy. In the United States and Germany, they were almost zero for years which opened up a wide range of opportunities for investors. On the other hand, in Russia and Kazakhstan, the interest rates are high which limits borrowing but at the same time helps to keep inflation under control (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Monetary Policy Tightening and Divergent Interest Rate Strategies (2015–2023)

This chart compares central bank interest rates in Uzbekistan, Russia, Kazakhstan, the United States, and Germany from 2015 to 2023, illustrating how each economy calibrates monetary policy in response to inflation, economic shocks, and financial stability concerns. Uzbekistan maintains relatively high policy rates throughout the period, peaking at 15% in 2020—a reflection of inflationary pressure and the need to stabilize the national currency. Russia follows a generally downward trend until 2020, after which rates rise sharply, hitting 14% in 2022 amid geopolitical tensions, capital outflows, and elevated inflation.

Kazakhstan's rates gradually decline until 2019, then increase again during the post-pandemic inflation wave, also reaching a peak of 14.5% in 2022. In contrast, the USA and Germany start with exceptionally low interest rates, even reaching near-zero or negative levels in Germany. However, both countries pivot abruptly in 2022 as global inflation surges, with the USA raising rates to 4% and Germany to nearly 4% by 2023.

The data reveals a synchronized global tightening cycle beginning in 2021–2022, while also highlighting structural differences: emerging economies rely on higher rates to curb volatility, whereas advanced economies shift gradually from historically accommodative to restrictive policies.

The most important indicator is the real wage. It shows a person's standard of living and the real value of labor. In Uzbekistan, the real incomes are still fighting against inflation. However, Russia and Kazakhstan have observed relatively stable growth. In the US and Germany, on the other hand, real wages are barely changing due to the low inflation, which is a sign of economic stability (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Real Wage Growth and Purchasing Power Trends (2015–2023)

This chart illustrates real wages—adjusted for inflation—in Uzbekistan, Russia, Kazakhstan, the United States, and Germany from 2015 to 2023. Overall, all five countries show positive real wage dynamics, though at markedly different levels and growth rates. Uzbekistan displays steady improvement from roughly USD 200 in 2015 to around USD 400 in 2023, reflecting gradual increases in nominal wages that outpace inflation in the long run. Russia and Kazakhstan exhibit similar upward movements, with real wages rising from about USD 450 to nearly USD 900 in Russia and from USD 500 to roughly USD 650 in Kazakhstan. Despite occasional inflation shocks, both countries maintain long-term gains in purchasing power.

In advanced economies, the USA and Germany maintain substantially higher real wage levels. The United States rises from approximately USD 4,700 to nearly USD 5,900, demonstrating robust economic fundamentals and stable productivity growth. Germany shows moderate but consistent improvement, climbing from just over USD 4,000 to around USD 5,000 in 2023.

Overall, the data confirms widening gaps in global wage purchasing power, with advanced economies far ahead, yet also highlights meaningful progress in emerging markets.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In comparison, despite the progress achieved by today's economy, there has been little noticeable improvement in people's living standards. When reports are discussed, the indicators show growth, yet in reality, life more difficult, real purchasing power weakens, and even when salaries rise, prices rise faster. The volume of credit is also increasing, but along with it, obligations grow, turning the picture of freedom into one of dependency. This is no longer merely a financial issue it is a question of meaning.

After all, the economy was created for human beings, and humans should not become its servants. If labor does not bring a person peace, confidence, and recognition, then somewhere the system has gone wrong. In developed countries such as the United State or Germany, economic growth is slow but steady, people trust tomorrow. In contrast, in countries like Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, and Russia, growth rapid but unstable. The numbers rise, while real life lags behind. The true expansion of the economy is not achieved merely by increasing GDP, but by improving the quality of life. Because genuine wealth is a society where a person can live in peace, freedom, and dignity – as the fair reward for the labors.

List of used literature:

1. World Bank (2024). World Development Indicators Database. Retrieved from <https://data.worldbank.org>
2. International Monetary Fund (IMF) (2023). World Economic Outlook: Navigating Global Divergences. Washington, D.C.
3. OECD (2022). Employment Outlook 2022: Building Back Fairer. Paris: OECD Publishing.
4. Rosstat (2023). Statistical Yearbook of the Russian Federation. Moscow.
5. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Markaziy banki (2023). Yillik hisobot: Pul-kredit siyosati va iqtisodiy barqarorlik. Toshkent.
6. Qozog'iston Respublikasi Milliy banki (2023). Makroiqtisodiy sharhlar va inflyatsiya tahlili. Ostona.
7. U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics (2023). Economic Situation Summary: Real Earnings and Inflation Trends. Washington.
8. Destatis (2023). Federal Statistical Office of Germany: Economic Indicators and Wages. Berlin.
9. Edmondson, A. C. (1999). Psychological Safety and Learning Behavior in Work Teams. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 44(2), 350–383.
10. Spector, P. E. (1985). Measurement of Human Job Satisfaction: Development of the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS). *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 13(6), 693–713.
11. Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J. (1995). MLQ Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire. Mind Garden, Palo Alto, CA.
12. Stiglitz, J. E. (2012). *The Price of Inequality: How Today's Divided Society Endangers Our Future*. New York: W.W. Norton & Company.
13. Sen, A. (1999). *Development as Freedom*. Oxford University Press.

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